

Influence of Online Media Use and Parental Education on the Holistic Self-Care of Secondary School Students in Post-COVID-19 Northeast Thailand

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Abstract

Background: Secondary school students in Northeast Thailand have been experiencing an increase in online media usage following the COVID-19 pandemic. As many learning activities are conducted online, this has the potential to impact their physical and mental health.

Objective: This study aimed to examine the holistic self-care approaches of Secondary school students using online media in the post-COVID-19 pandemic in Northeast Thailand.

Methodology: This study was a descriptive research with a sample group of 322 Secondary school students. The data collection instruments were questionnaires on general characteristics, online media use, health problems, and holistic self-care. Five experts with diverse expertise assessed the quality of the instruments. The content validity index (CVI) was found to be 0.88, and reliability yielded a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.96. The data were analysed using descriptive statistics (frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviations), Pearson correlation, and stepwise multiple regression statistics.

Results: The study showed that the sample was women (55.40%), with a mean age of 14.49 years (SD = 1.58). Their parents' education was mostly at the secondary level (40.30%). They used online media daily (55.90%), with an average duration of 4.95 hours per day (SD = 2.27). They used smartphones the most (94.60%). In terms of health problems, the physical and intellectual aspects were found to be at a moderate level, with average scores of 32.45 points (SD = 9.93) and 34.32 points (SD = 0.59), respectively. The emotional and social aspects were at a high level, with an average score of 44.65 points (SD = 7.63) and 29.85 points (SD = 4.95). Also,

holistic self-care was at a moderate level, with a mean score of 176.50 (SD = 44.72). Moreover, factors such as the type of internet used, duration of use, devices, and parents' educational level have a statistically significant influence on the holistic self-care of Secondary school students ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusion: This study emphasises the significance of holistic self-care for Secondary school students in relation to their online media use, considering factors such as internet type, duration of use, devices, and parents' educational level.

Unique Contribution: This study provides empirical data showing the use of online media by Secondary school students in various contexts. Parents with a high level of education will positively impact the holistic self-care of Secondary school students.

Key Recommendation: This finding provides a direct, actionable focus for the cooperation between parents and schools. Specifically, suggest that cooperation should focus on monitoring two key areas: reducing the number of accessible devices and reducing the duration of use to boost holistic self-care immediately.

Keywords: Secondary School Students; Health Problems; Holistic Self-care; Using Online Media; COVID-19

Introduction

The global reopening of countries since the COVID-19 pandemic has led to new patterns of holistic self-care for SSSs. In Thailand, 36.54% of all students in rural and urban schools must deal with pre-existing issues in physical, mental, social, and intellectual self-care. Previous research has shown that the self-care behaviour of Thai students is positively associated with actual use of self-care, learner interaction, and behavioural intention (Kornpitack & Sawmong, 2022). Studies indicate that holistic self-care during the post-COVID-19 pandemic period involves identity exploration, gaining confidence, increased social interaction, seeking acceptance from society and peers, and engaging in learning new things through online media (Octavius et al., 2020).

Even though the Thai government declared October 1, 2022, as the end of the COVID-19 public health emergency, online media use among SSSs remains the highest-risk group across all age groups. Previous studies have shown that most Thai SSSs have access to the internet (90%), with 98.5% using smartphones during the post-COVID-19 pandemic period. SSSs mostly use the internet to communicate on social networks, search for information, and watch movies, shows, and videos. As previously observed, new users spend an average of 11 hours and 25 minutes per day on the internet, while SSSs spend, on average, 12 hours and 8 minutes per day. The Northeast residents spend the most time online, with an average of 12 hours and 29 minutes a day (Insight Era, 2024). However, studies on students using online media for more than 1 hour per day and an average of 3 days per week can compare the differences in the effects on health problems, because using online media for only a short period of time is considered the beginning of the signal to signal health problems (Wonginchan et al., 2024).

The majority of SSSs in Thailand experience health problems related to online media use, which is greater than the global average of 56% (Mongkhon et al., 2021). Physical health problems can arise due to the presence of risks, including neck pain, shoulder pain, back pain, physical

weakness, poor physical movement, and unhealthy eating. Emotional health problems, such as stress, anxiety, depression, insomnia, and abnormal sleep cycles, can affect online learning. Social health issues arise for SSSs who utilise online learning due to their lack of social interaction, cyber-bullying, online harassment, biased associations, violence issues, and concerns about personal privacy. Intellectual health issues include difficulty concentrating, learning, preparing, socialising, and maintaining daily habits/routines (Li, 2022).

When a health problem arises in one aspect, if it is not treated correctly, it can have more severe consequences or impact other health issues. For example, when an individual looks at a screen for an extended period, these symptoms can cause immediate headaches, inflammation, premature degeneration, muscle fatigue, and pain. SSSs who are infatuated with games may become overweight or obese, which can lead to a lack of self-confidence, increased anxiety, and stress (Yan et al., 2021). Online media use for SSS who have learning difficulties may affect long-term learning performance, sense of responsibility, sense of inferiority, and gaming addiction (Wartberg et al., 2019). Therefore, the care and prevention of problems may utilise the principles of holistic healthcare, which encompasses the care of all aspects of health, including physical, emotional, social, and intellectual well-being (George et al., 2020).

This is the first study on holistic self-care to be conducted among SSSs in Northeast Thailand after the COVID-19 pandemic. To serve as a guideline for promoting self-care for high school students. This study aims to examine the holistic self-care necessary to provide comprehensive physical, emotional, social, and intellectual healthcare to SSSs who use online media in the post-COVID-19 pandemic era in Northeast Thailand.

Theoretical framework and previous studies

This study employs a holistic approach to healthcare. George et al. (2020) explained that receiving good physical and mental care can lead to positive outcomes in other aspects of a person's health. However, if there is an impact on one aspect of health, be it physical, emotional, social, or intellectual, it tends to affect other aspects of health as well. This concept helps SSSs to be aware of the threats posed by online media use and to take care of their health in all aspects. However, there are still challenges in implementing holistic self-care, taking into account relevant factors and conditions such as the need to use online media, appropriate duration of use, device quality, self-control, and parental supervision (Wonginchan et al., 2024). Despite the challenges mentioned above, collaboration between SSSs and relevant personnel will help develop a more effective, holistic approach to self-care.

Despite these concerns, little research has been conducted to examine the holistic self-care of SSSs in such a context. Meine et al (2021) focused on health literacy, resilience, and well-being in the post-COVID-19 pandemic period. At the same time, Barnett et al (2021) have further studied organisational-theory-guided holistic self-caring. Black & Taylor (2021) highlighted that the context of online media use has increased the use of already-existing holistic student self-assessment, which is typically expressed through emergency aid and resources in a personalised, contextualised, and resource-sensitive manner. Overall, the aforementioned study emphasises the

importance of health education, self-assessment, and the appropriate use of resources among SSSs to achieve better quality self-care.

Study objectives

1. To study health problems and holistic self-care of SSSs from using online media in the post-COVID-19 pandemic Northeast Thailand.
2. To study the holistic self-care approach of SSSs through online media use in the post-COVID-19 pandemic Northeast Thailand.

Methodology

Design

A multiple regression analysis was utilised to examine holistic self-care practices conducted among SSSs in Northeast Thailand following the COVID-19 pandemic. The study of physical, emotional, social, and intellectual healthcare revealed key advantages of the multiple regression design. Methodological flaws in multiple regression that could potentially cause reduced bias were identified. The evidence of possible causality between variables and outcomes increases with the greater internal validity of the study.

Setting

The study was conducted in Northeast Thailand, specifically chosen because it encompasses two distinct contexts: rural and urban schools. This dual-context approach is essential because rural and urban settings differ significantly in factors known to moderate online media health risks among adolescents. Regarding the risk of health problems from online media, considering the concept of internet access, the opportunity to access internet network services varied for each person when needed (Mersereau, 2021). This means that SSSs living in urban areas are likely to have more convenience and flexibility in using the internet than SSSs living in rural areas. They will have more opportunities to use online media. Rural students may face limited access to devices, but they could experience different supervision dynamics due to factors such as parental work migration or agricultural schedules. These contextual differences necessitate studying both settings to identify context-specific vulnerabilities and develop targeted intervention strategies for promoting holistic self-care.

The Upper Northeast was Khon Kaen Province, and the Lower Northeast was Ubon Ratchathani Province in Thailand, comprising 6 districts. All selected study settings of the Provincial Education Office have been scaled up through a partnership between counties with rural and urban schools. The study sites were chosen because they were ready to launch a complete cycle of private, public, and special education schools.

Samples and sampling

Sample sizes were determined using the G*Power software for social and behavioural research. The statistical test is specified as G*Power using test > means > two independent groups for small effects ($p < 0.01, 0.15, \text{ and } 0.99$). Thus, the effect size was arbitrarily determined, which is the logical rationale for the arbitrarily selected effect size. Accordingly, a sample size of 306 participants was selected; however, we increased the sample size by 5%. After completion, we

decided to use data from 322 participants who are representative of urban and rural schools in Khon Kaen and Ubon Ratchathani provinces, Northeast Thailand.

In the first step, the sample was divided into two clusters: Khon Kaen, located in the upper northeastern region, and Ubon Ratchathani, situated in the lower northeastern region. Additionally, each province had one urban school and two rural schools, totalling six schools across the two provinces. In the second step, we used stratified random sampling as the quota method for each subgroup of students, divided into urban areas with 160 SSSs (80 SSSs per school) and rural areas with 162 SSSs (40-41 SSSs per school). In the third step, we used simple random assignments, using a lottery method to select the number of SSSs as permitted by the school. Finally, we randomly sampled 322 SSSs and had them complete a questionnaire.

Eligibility Criteria

The inclusion criteria were as follows: (i) using online media for more than 1 hour per day and an average of 3 days per week; (ii) able to participate online via computer or smartphone; (iii) able to participate in the study; and (iv) participation and willingness to provide informed consent. The exclusion criteria were as follows: (i) inability to participate fully, (ii) moving to another school, and (iii) withdrawal from the study.

Measures

Each item to assess holistic self-care and health problems was rated on a 5-point Likert scale, with a range of 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). Five experts with diverse expertise validated the instruments. The content validity index (CVI) of the questionnaires was found to be 0.88. Holistic self-care was assessed according to four aspects: physical, emotional, social, and intellectual healthcare. The instrument was tested on a sample of 30 SSSs with similar characteristics to the target sample to determine its reliability, yielding a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.96. The respondents' data included gender, age, number of siblings, parents' education levels, and parental occupation. Information on online media use obtained from the questionnaire included the average duration of use per day, starting at 1 hour per day or more, and the average duration of use per week, starting at 3 days or more. The interpretation of using online media was divided into three levels: low, moderate, and high. The range value was calculated by subtracting the lowest value from the highest value and dividing the result into three categories. The interpretation of the results of holistic self-care is divided into three levels of scores: low level (65.00-153.67 points), moderate level (153.68-242.34 points), and high level (242.35-325.00 points). The interpretation of health problems encompasses various aspects, as follows: physical and emotional aspects, categorised as follows: low level (12.00-28.00 points), moderate level (28.01-44.00 points), and high level (44.01-60.00 points). Social aspects: low level equal to 8.00-18.67 points, moderate level equal to 18.68-29.34 points, and high level equal to 29.35-40.00 points. As for intellectual aspects: low level equal to 13.00-30.33 points, moderate level equal to 30.34-47.66 points, and high level equal to 47.67-65.00 points.

Data Collection

The school administrators permitted the research team to collect data in accordance with the research objectives. Research team members, who had passed a human research ethics class, were tasked with explaining the details and objectives of the study to respondents. All sample

groups completed the questionnaire in approximately 30 to 40 minutes. The following steps were involved in the data collection process. First, the research team had to maintain social distancing and wear face masks while on site. The researchers used a simple random sampling method to select the sample, and the sample was willing to participate in the study. Second, after receiving permission from their parents to participate in the research project, the participants who agreed to answer the questionnaire were able to respond through a Google form. The research team assisted and supported SSSs in completing the questionnaire and providing their answers online. However, SSSs responded to the questionnaire between April and June 2023.

Data Analysis

The IBM SPSS software package version 29.0.2 for Windows was utilised for all statistical analyses. The data were analysed by using descriptive statistics, which included frequencies, percentages, minimums, maximums, means, standard deviations (SD), mean deviations (MD), and interquartile ranges (IQR). Pearson's correlation coefficient was used to analyse the relationships between variables. Stepwise statistics were used in the model to analyse holistic self-care due to the exploratory nature of this study. This method was selected to identify the most parsimonious subset of predictors from the available variables, as there were no prior theoretical expectations about which predictors would be significant. The relationship between physical, emotional, social, and intellectual healthcare is impacted by reported holistic self-care, which had a statistically significant moderating effect. Multivariate regression analysis was conducted with significance set at $p \leq 0.05$.

Results

The sample's demographic characteristics

According to the descriptive analysis of SSSs who used online media, the majority of the sample were female (55.4%), with an average age of 14.49 years ($SD = 1.58$). The number of siblings, including the student, was 2 (42.5%), and the IQR was 2 persons ($MD = 1.52$). Most live with both parents (46.8%). Most parents were farmers (37.8%), and 40.3% of them had secondary education. The analysis of using online learning by SSSs showed that prepaid and postpaid internet technologies were the most popular (37.4% and 36.9%). The average duration of use per day was 4.95 hours ($SD = 2.27$), and the average duration of use per week was 5.69 days ($SD = 1.62$). Social networks such as Facebook and Line were the most frequently used online media activities, accounting for 46.0% of the sample. The most used form of online connection among SSSs was smartphones, at 94.6%. Table 1 outlines the sample's demographic characteristics.

Table 1: The sample's demographic characteristics (N=322)

	No. of respondents	%
Gender		
Male	144	44.6
Female	178	55.4
Age (Mean = 14.49, SD = 1.58)		
12–13 years old	93	28.8
14–15 years old	159	49.5
16–18 years old	70	21.6

	No. of respondents	%
Number of siblings (IQR=2, MD=1.52)		
1	34	10.5
2	137	42.5
3–4	115	35.7
> or = 5	36	11.3
Parents		
Both parents	151	46.8
Father or mother	67	20.7
Relative	104	32.5
Parental occupation		
Farmer	122	37.8
Business owner or employee	100	31.1
Government or state enterprise	32	9.9
Housewife or Others	68	21.2
Parental education level		
Primary education	117	36.3
Secondary education	130	40.3
Associate degree or above	75	23.4
Internet types		
Prepaid mobile phones	120	37.4
Postpaid mobile phones	119	36.9
Broadband internet	83	25.7
Duration of use per day (M = 4.95, SD = 2.27)		
1–3 hours	90	27.9
4–5 hours	104	32.4
6–7 hours	80	24.8
> or = 8 hours	48	14.9
Duration of use per week (M = 5.69, SD = 1.62)		
3 days	58	18.0
4-6 days	84	26.1
Every day	180	55.9
Activities performed		
Social Network	148	46.0
Entertainment	87	27.0
Knowledge or others	87	27.0
Devices used		
Smartphone	305	94.6
iPad	10	3.2
Notebook or others	7	2.2

Holistic self-care and health problems

The level of holistic self-care was moderate, with a mean score of 176.50 (SD = 44.72). The average score for health problems was high, including emotional (mean = 44.65, SD = 7.63) and social (mean = 29.85, SD = 4.95) health problems. Additionally, the average score for health problems was moderate, encompassing both physical (mean = 32.45, SD = 9.93) and intellectual (mean = 34.32, SD = 10.59) health issues. Table 2 provides information on the study variables.

Table 2: Holistic self-care and health problems.

Variables	Min	Max	Mean	SD	Level
Holistic self-care	65.00	314.00	176.50	44.72	moderate
Health problem					
Physical	12	60	32.45	9.93	moderate
Emotional	12	60	44.65	7.63	high
Social	8	40	29.85	4.95	high
Intellectual	13	65	34.32	10.59	moderate

Online media use and holistic self-care

The study results found that the holistic self-care of SSSs from using online media after the COVID-19 pandemic was 20.3 per cent ($R^2 = 0.203$). The equation for the holistic self-care of SSSs from using online media can be written as follows:

$$Y = 2.540 + .194X1 - .345X2 - .097X3 + .094X4$$

Y refers to the holistic self-care of SSSs through the use of online media.

X1 means that when parents' education level increases by one level, it will result in SSSs increasing their holistic self-care through online media use by 0.194 units.

X2 means that when the number of devices used increases by one level, it will result in SSSs reducing their holistic self-care from using online media by 0.345 units.

X3 means that when duration (days per week) increases by one level, it will result in SSSs reducing their holistic self-care from using online media by 0.097 units.

X4 means that when internet types increase by one level, it will result in SSSs increasing their holistic self-care from using online media by 0.094 units.

Factors of using online media have a statistically significant influence on the holistic self-care of SSSs ($p < 0.05$), ranked from least to most as follows: Internet type (Beta = 0.147), duration (Beta = 0.161), devices used (Beta = 0.209), and parents' education level (Beta = 0.219). Table 3 depicts the use of online media and holistic self-care.

Table 3: Using online media and holistic self-care.

Factors	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	p value
	β	SE			
(Constant)	2.540	0.195		10.052	0.000
X ₁ : Parents' education levels	0.194*	0.058	0.219	3.354	0.001
X ₂ : Devices used	- 0.345*	0.106	- 0.209	- 3.257	0.001
X ₃ : Duration (days per week)	- 0.097*	0.049	- 0.161	-1.992	0.045
X ₄ : Internet type	0.094*	0.042	0.147	2.248	0.026

*Note: $R^2 = 0.203$, Adjusted $R^2 = 0.191$, $*p < 0.05$*

Discussion

This study revealed several important patterns. Students demonstrated moderate levels of holistic self-care ($M = 176.50$, $SD = 44.72$) alongside moderate-to-high levels of health problems, with emotional ($M = 44.65$, $SD = 7.63$) and social difficulties ($M = 29.85$, $SD = 4.95$) being particularly pronounced. A critical alternative interpretation of our findings warrants explicit consideration: holistic self-care may not simply deteriorate in response to health problems but may rather serve as an active coping mechanism. That is, SSSs who experience more physical, emotional, social, or intellectual problems are more aware of their need and are actively engaging in more self-care to mitigate the issues. Importantly, this interpretation implies that problems do not directly lead to a decline in self-care; instead, they act as perceived threats that stimulate compensatory self-care behaviours. The findings align with previous studies. This suggests that holistic self-care among students is associated with resilient self-care, psychological self-care, theory-guided holistic self-care, and neoliberal self-care (Meine et al., 2021; Barnett et al., 2021). Furthermore, it has been identified that long-term holistic self-care, which enables individuals to manage physical health problems and promote social well-being, plays a role in the relationship between mental and physical health (Paterson et al., 2022).

The study results found that physical health problems were at a moderate level ($M = 32.45$). Although the mean score did not reach the high-level cutoff (44.01 points), the relatively large standard deviation reveals considerable variability, indicating that a portion of students experience more pronounced physical difficulties. Even moderate physical health issues during adolescence are concerning, since this period strongly influences health patterns later in life (Patton et al., 2016). The data indicate that the severity of this problem is a growing concern rather than being comfortably controlled, so cooperation between parents and schools to encourage SSSs to engage in outdoor activities and reduce online screen time is essential and should be continuously monitored (Ercan et al., 2021). The types of activities related to addressing the physical health issues, such as physical health complications, self-reported physical activity, and students' healthy physical activities. There are also different physical roles in students' functioning, mobility, and usual activities of internet usage (de Guevara Rodríguez et al., 2024). At the same time, the social health problems were at almost a high level (mean = 29.85). Previous studies have confirmed the key role of holistic self-care strategies, including elements of family support, coping strategies, and social healing, providing evidence of a link between holistic self-care and social health problems. For example, a recent study conducted in multiple centres found that COVID-19-enforced learning isolation had a significant impact on social inactivity, as measured by students' engagement, perceived learning support, and frustration with learning (Wei et al., 2022).

Furthermore, holistic self-care was positively correlated with the emotional health of SSSs. This finding further highlights the importance of mental health because it is associated with poor functional outcomes and long-term use of online media. This is consistent with research regarding two mental health problems of the post-pandemic period, which found that mental

health-related shocks are related to the provision of psychological services and post-traumatic stress in learners. There have been reports of a link between workplace conditions, academic decline, medical comorbidities, uncertainties, stigma, prolonged isolation, social rejection, work stress, and learning burnout (Vadivel et al., 2021). This may be because mental health is more prone to online learning stressors, or leads to a higher rate of reporting psychological symptoms (Zhao et al., 2021). Moreover, the intellectual health problems of SSSs after the COVID-19 pandemic have several implications. First, the intellectual health of SSSs is likely to experience lower creativity, curiosity, critical thinking, and problem-solving skills due to their increased risk of learning fatigue. Second, a lack of family support impacts their mental health in terms of online learning and skills development. Third, due to the extended period of mandatory online learning, intellectual health is likely to face more financial, cognitive, learning, concentration, and holistic self-care issues. Finally, intellectual health is linked to learning online after the COVID-19 pandemic. It is also linked to the use of self-learning strategies, engaging in academic learning activities, and reflecting on learning (Milroy et al., 2021).

The regression results show that an increase in the number of devices used (X2) and the duration of use (days per week) (X3) leads to a reduction in holistic self-care. Argue that the increased availability/dependency on online media inherently creates environments (e.g., more sedentary behaviour, social comparison, poor sleep due to screen time) that displace or inhibit healthy self-care behaviours (Ercan et al., 2021). As the rise of internet types increases (X4), so does the increasing choice of online media (e.g., postpaid mobile phones that allow for various time limits), which in turn reduces sedentary behaviour and promotes better self-care.

Practical Implications

The practical implications of this study could be beneficial for holistic self-care in Northeast Thailand. The findings suggest potential strategies to alleviate physical, social, mental, and intellectual health issues for SSSs during the post-COVID-19 pandemic period. According to Barnett et al. (2021) and Paterson et al. (2022) regarding holistic self-care after the COVID-19 pandemic, we extended the practical implications for understanding how to apply students' healthy physical activities, coping strategies, mental health-related shocks, and problem-solving skills. Collaborative planning with multiple stakeholders, including students, parents, health care personnel, and school administrators, is essential to promote self-care among SSSs to improve their physical, emotional, social, and intellectual health.

Theoretical Implications

The results of this study have offered theoretical implications that relate to existing previous works (Meine et al., 2021), the global perspective (Li, 2022), the international approach, cross-national regions, and single approaches to holistic self-care (Kornpitack & Sawmong, 2022). Many studies have not provided findings for a specific group, as they have utilised literature reviews (Peterson et al., 2022), a qualitative design, and a quantitative method (Kornpitack & Sawmong, 2022). Our results have clearly filled the theoretical gap regarding holistic self-care in relation to physical, social, mental, and intellectual health (Mongkon et al., 2021). Hence, this

result informs us of the significant influence of holistic self-care, and we found that SSSs experienced its positive effects during the post-COVID-19 pandemic period.

Potential Limitations and Future Study

The limitations of this study provide opportunities for future research. The first study is to ensure that SSSs adopt holistic self-care during the post-COVID-19 pandemic period in Northeast Thailand. Second, online questionnaires were the only source of data used for analyses in this study. Third, the post-pandemic period was investigated in relation to SSSs' holistic self-care, using a small sample size. Fourth, a single study design was employed, which may not be representative of other regions. Thus, the results cannot be generalised to the entire picture of all students in other contexts. Although the participants provided valuable insights, the results only relate to holistic self-care for SSSs. In addition, further studies could focus on mixed-method research (in-depth interview design integrated with quantitative findings) regarding holistic self-care among SSSs, so that the findings can be added to existing empirical models.

Conclusions

Research results indicate that promoting holistic self-care for SSSs through online media use precautions in Northeast Thailand was at a moderate level, and physical and intellectual health problems were at a moderate level, while emotional and social health problems were at a high level. However, this moderate average masks a critical concern: a significant proportion of participants exhibited high emotional and social health problems coupled with online media dependency, indicating that current prevention and promotion strategies are insufficient. The risk of developing health problems varies considerably across individuals, necessitating tailored interventions for vulnerable populations. They emphasise that the risk of developing health problems varies from person to person, necessitating tailored interventions for vulnerable populations. Furthermore, this study revealed differences in parental attention and ability to encourage SSSs to adopt a holistic approach to self-care through the use of diverse online media, taking into account factors such as gender, age, number of siblings, parents, parental occupation, parental education level, internet type, duration of use per day, duration of use per week, activities used, devices, and health problems. It is therefore important to encourage SSSs to take care of their health in all aspects whenever they use online media, using practical and effective strategies, including having clear agreements on the time spent online, raising parental awareness of online threats, and supporting the use of appropriate devices and developing differentiated support based on individual risk profiles. In addition, collaboration between schools and parents is likely to contribute to the greater success of SSSs' holistic prevention and self-care efforts, particularly for those exhibiting high emotional and social vulnerabilities. Ultimately, the result is that they are healthy in all aspects: physically, emotionally, socially, and intellectually.

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